

The International Interdisciplinary Scientific Conference

"Digital Horizons 2024: Innovation, Ethics, and Dialogue in a Connected World"

24th May 2024, University of Economics in Bratislava, Slovakia

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

BRATISLAVA, 2024

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

Editors: Anetta Čaplánová – Eva Sirakovová

Reviewers:

prof. Ibrahim Sirkeci, PhD., International Business School, Manchester, United Kingdom
Andrej Příklad, PhD., University of Economics in Bratislava, Slovakia

Publisher:

Vydavateľstvo EKONÓM (Publishing House)
Dolnozemska cesta 1
852 35 Bratislava
Slovak Republic

Year of publishing: 2024

ISBN: 978-80-2205-5146-5

This publication was prepared in the framework of the project Overcoming Digital Divide in Europe and Southeast Asia “ODDEA”
Project No. 101086381
Call: HORIZON-MSCA-2021-SE-01-1

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Foreword

In the dynamic and evolving landscape of the digital age, the **Digital Horizons 2024** conference organized at the University of Economics in Bratislava provides the opportunity to discuss interdisciplinary issues linked to the ongoing processes of digitalization, innovation, ethics, and dialogue in our increasingly interconnected world. This volume of abstracts provides the insights in the spectrum of research topics undertaken by the researchers within the ODDEA project, but also the interdisciplinary topics of the scholarly discourse by other researchers attending this event.

The papers presented at the conference on 24th May 2024 document the profound impact that digital technologies have on every aspect of our lives. The conference theme "Innovation, Ethics and Dialogue in a Connected World" not only highlights technological advancements that drive progress, but it also focuses on ethical considerations and the necessity for ongoing dialogue to ensure that these innovations benefit the society as a whole.

The digital revolution not only brought unprecedented opportunities but is connected also with challenges. From the discussion of how artificial intelligence transforms government human resource management to digital startups that foster inclusivity in Southeast Asia, the papers presented at this conference reflect a broad spectrum of issues and solutions. Each abstract within this volume documents an aspect of the diverse and rich intellectual landscape related to key theme of the conference.

In the following pages, the reader has the opportunity to explore a variety of topics, which are at the core of digital transformation and its societal implications. These include such topics as the trust dynamics of PromptPay users in Bangkok, which are studied using an interdisciplinary approach using the insights from economics, technology, and psychology. A comprehensive literature review on AI-powered digital transformation in government sectors brings forward the key role of policy makers and governance to navigate the digital era.

The topics also focus on regional studies that illustrate the varied pace and nature of digital adoption and its impacts. The regions include South-East Asia and focus on such topics as the analysis of digital development among the top ASEAN countries, which also raise important questions about convergence and divergence in digital growth. The exploration of eGovernment initiatives in Indonesia from the perspective of institutional theory brings light into the evolution of governance.

The core focus of the ODDEA project is based on bridging the digital divide between European regions and South-East Asia. The research on intersectional digital divide in Indonesia, or on ICT distribution in ASEAN nations highlights the disparities that persist across ASEAN countries despite their rapid technological advancements. This research points to the critical need for developing inclusive policies that would ensure equitable access to digital resources.

The fintech industry, which is a cornerstone of the modern economy, is also focus of research of participating researchers, including the focus on the development and impact on traditional banking structures in Southeast Asia. This research emphasizes the transformative potential of digital finance and its implications for economic stability and growth.

The volume addresses also such country related topics as the digital transformation of family businesses in Thailand pointing out to the need for traditional enterprises to adapt in an increasingly digital marketplace. The exploration of digital media transformations highlights the challenges and innovations of sustaining media businesses in Southeast Asia.

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Currently, one of the hot topics in the digitalization research is the discussion of the role of digital currencies. The study on CBDCs in the EU provides a concise look at how digital currencies shape trust and financial integration in a diverse regulatory landscape.

Education represents a pillar of social development. The comparative study on English language education for future innovators in Montenegro and Poland reflects the need for broader educational reforms to prepare the next generation for a global digital economy.

The importance of e-payment systems in enhancing government operations is considered on the example of Thailand's PromptPay system focusing on the efficiency gains and economic benefits of digital financial systems.

As we look to a future, where digitalization is expected to exponentially accelerate, the need for robust, inclusive, and ethical framework becomes critical. We find it important that the research presented in this volume not only addresses current challenges, but it also focuses on future innovations that are needed to align technological progress with the respect for equity, transparency, and sustainability.

I extend my gratitude to all the contributors, reviewers, and organizers of the **Digital Horizons 2024** conference. Their dedication and scholar rigor have made this event a rewarding academic experience, the forum for knowledge exchange and a catalyst for positive changes and overcoming digital divide in our digital world.

Anetta Caplanova

Editor and ODDEA project coordinator

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Are they really “Prompt (พร้อม - ready)” to continue? The Mystery of Continuous Usage Intention through Perceived Trust Among People in Bangkok

Panisa Arthachinda

International College, National Institute of
Development Administration
Serithai Road
Klong-Chan, Bangkok, Bangkok
Thailand
panisa.art@gmail.com

Anetta Čaplánová

University of Economics in Bratislava
Department of Economics, Faculty of
Economics and Finance
Dolnozemska cesta 1
Bratislava, 852 35
Slovakia
anetta.caplanova@euba.sk

Lubomir Darmo

University of Economics in Bratislava
Department of Economics, Faculty of Economics
and Finance
Dolnozemska cesta 1
Bratislava, 852 35
Slovakia
e-mail: lubomir.darmo@euba.sk

Abstract

PromptPay is Thailand's payment system allowing users to transfer money using their citizen ID or mobile phone number. Also, PromptPay provides a variety of supplementary services and aims to be a leading national e-payment in the forthcoming period. However, many studies have revealed an ongoing trust concern regarding the use of the service, which affects their willingness to continue. This leads to the aims of this study to investigate the effect of perceived trust on satisfaction and emotional engagement of users of PromptPay service in Bangkok, as well as to analyze the subsequent impact on continued usage intention. Additionally, we also study if the effect of satisfaction and emotional engagement on continued usage intention can be moderated by switching barrier factors. Survey data is planned to be obtained from respondents living in Bangkok (downtown, midtown, and urban Bangkok). We will use Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) to analyze the data.

JEL classification: D83, G21, L86

Keywords: perceived trust, continue usage intention, satisfaction, emotional engagement, switching barrier, e-payment, PromptPay

Acknowledgment: This outcome was prepared in the framework of the project Overcoming Digital Divide in Europe and Southeast Asia “ODDEA” Project No. 101086381 Call: HORIZON-MSCA-2021-SE-01-1

**Co-funded by
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AI-Powered Digital Transformation of Government Human Resource Management: A Five-Year Systematic Literature Review from 2019 to 2023

Xiangyu Bian

National Institute of Development Administration, Thailand
International College.

19th Floor Navamindrathiraj Building, 148 Serithai Road, Klong-Chan, Bangkok
Bangkok, 10240

Thailand

e-mail: yibianjiayou@gmail.com

Abstract

In the past five years, the rapid development of artificial intelligence technology has spurred profound changes in government human resource management. Governments and public sector organizations worldwide are actively harnessing the power of artificial intelligence to reshape human resource management practices and optimize talent management. This paper adopts the PRISMA systematic literature review method to comprehensively explore the digital transformation of government human resource management driven by artificial intelligence. The study found that policy and governance innovation are crucial, and future research should explore the establishment of more adaptive and inclusive regulatory frameworks to balance technological innovation with public interests. Additionally, ethical and moral issues also require continuous attention and in-depth research, especially in addressing concerns such as privacy protection, data security, and algorithm bias, for which corresponding solutions and regulatory standards need to be proposed. Furthermore, technological capabilities and organizational change are key to successful application of artificial intelligence in the public sector, and future research should further explore new theoretical perspectives, strengthen interdisciplinary cooperation, expand empirical research methods, explore policy and practice, and pay more attention to aspects such as data security and privacy protection.

JEL classification: H83, O33, J45

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence; Government

Acknowledgment: This outcome was prepared in the framework of the project Overcoming Digital Divide in Europe and Southeast Asia “ODDEA” Project No. 101086381 Call: HORIZON-MSCA-2021-SE-01-1

**Co-funded by
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Artificial intelligence in the digital transformation of enterprises

Jerzy Duda

AGH University of Science and Technology
al. Mickiewicza 30
Kraków, 30-059, Poland
e-mail: jduda@agh.edu.pl

Joana Duda

AGH University of Science and Technology
al. Mickiewicza 30
Kraków, 30-059, Poland
e-mail: joduda@agh.edu.pl

Ivana Ognjanović

University of Donja Gorica
Oktoih 1
Podgorica, 81000
Montenegro
e-mail: ivana.ognjanovic@udg.edu.me

Ramo Sendelj

University of Donja Gorica
Oktoih 1
Podgorica, 81000
Montenegro
e-mail: ramo.sendelj@udg.edu.me

Abstract

AI is being gradually implemented in different industries and it will have a great influence on the economies of Europe and South-East Asia. Europe is one of the leaders in digitalization of its economy, including the adoption of AI, with Germany, France, and Scandinavian countries being at the forefront of such efforts. However, there is a significant gap regarding the AI readiness and adoption between those countries and such countries as Hungary, Slovakia, Poland or Balkan countries, according to the DESI Index. In South-East Asia, Singapore, Malaysia, and Thailand countries are investing in AI advancement, which is supported by the governments and private sectors. Nevertheless, in general, the region is still underdeveloped compared to Europe in terms of digital economies and AI adoption, as evidenced by the results of the ASEAN Digital Integration Index. Nevertheless, the economic implications of AI in fields like manufacturing, healthcare, and finance are still substantial. This paper is devoted to the implementation of AI in enterprises, focusing on aspects such as policy support, investment volumes, and qualified personnel. It will also look at the likely economic impacts and opportunities of AI, including productivity, changes on the demand and supply side, changes on the labor market, and AI governance. Drawing conclusions from the correlation between AI and digitalization indices – the paper is an attempt to see if Europe and South-Eastern Asia are ready for the AI-powered digital economy of the future.

JEL classification: C 63, C 88, D 22

Keywords: artificial intelligence, digital economy, AI adoption, digitalization of enterprises

Acknowledgment: This outcome was prepared in the framework of the project Overcoming Digital Divide in Europe and Southeast Asia “ODDEA” Project No. 101086381 Call: HORIZON-MSCA-2021-SE-01-1

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Digital development among top 5 ASEAN countries: Convergence or Divergence?

Azlina Hanif

Arshad Ayub Graduate Business School, Universiti Teknologi MARA
Level 3, Kompleks Al Farabi,
Shah Alam, 40450
Malaysia
e-mail: azlinahan@uitm.edu.my

Abstract

ASEAN is the fastest-growing internet market in the world. It envisions to become a leading digital community and economic bloc empowered by digital transformation. Despite ASEAN's rapid growth in digitalization, the level of digital development of its member countries is not uniform. As the digital economy is crucial in fostering economic growth, the present study provides an analysis of the digital transformation for ASEAN's top five countries namely Singapore, Brunei, Malaysia, Indonesia and Thailand. The main objective of the study is to determine if there is digital development convergence or divergence among the five countries. The indicators for digital development used are Fixed Broadband Subscription and Internet Use. The coefficient of variation obtained show that there is sigma convergence among the countries for both indicators of digital development. However, using panel data analysis, the beta coefficient for fixed broadband subscription shows divergence in digital development while the beta coefficient for internet use shows convergence at 10% significance level. Since the findings are contradictory, the present study aims to use other indicators to find confirmation about the nature of digital development for the top five ASEAN members.

JEL classification: E00, F02, O30

Keywords: digitalization, convergence, ASEAN

Acknowledgment: This outcome was prepared in the framework of the project Overcoming Digital Divide in Europe and Southeast Asia "ODDEA" Project No. 101086381 Call: HORIZON-MSCA-2021-SE-01-1

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Institutional Theory: Trajectory of eGovernment Initiatives in Indonesia

Kholid Haryono

Universitas Islam Indonesia
Department of Informatics
Yogyakarta, Indonesia
e-mail: kholid.haryono@uii.ac.id

Rafał Kusa

AGH University of Krakow
Faculty of Management
Gramatyka 10, 30-067
Krakow, Poland,
e-mail: rkusa@agh.edu.pl

Jerzy Duda

AGH University of Krakow, Faculty of
Management
al. Mickiewicza 30
Kraków, 30-059, Poland
e-mail: Jerzy.Duda@agh.edu.pl

Abstract

In 2022, Indonesia achieved an Electronic Government Digital Index (EGDI) score of 0.7160, ranking 77th out of 193 United Nations member states. This marks an improvement from the previous measurement in 2020, where Indonesia scored 0.6612, ranking 88th, and from 2018, with a score of 0.5258, ranking 107th. This improvement is attributed to various initiatives undertaken by the Indonesian government through implementation of Government System based on Electronic (SPBE). The initiative for accelerating digital transformation primarily began with bureaucratic reform, focusing on bureaucracy that directly impacts the public, a digital bureaucracy not reliant on paper, and an agile and fast bureaucracy. These three initiatives are related to the EGDI, which consists of three measurements: the Online Service Index (OSI), Telecommunication Infrastructure Index (TII), and Human Capital Index (HCI). Therefore, one of the expected impacts of the SPBE initiative is an increase in EGDI scores and rankings. This research aims to find out how the increase in EGDI obtained is related to the Indonesian government's initiative through the implementation of SPBE.

The approach used in this research is naturalistic interpretivism. This approach is suitable for research where the researcher is involved and participates directly in the process of the object being studied. The data was obtained through various forms and methods, including from the annual reports of the Ministry of Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform, which acts as the coordinator and authority holder for SPBE management. Among its authorities, it conducts SPBE monitoring and evaluation activities annually, and this data was collected over a five-year period from 2018 to 2022. The data was also obtained through socialization, workshops, and assessor training conducted annually from 2021 to 2023. These activities facilitated the researcher in understanding the data obtained and its context in relation to this research, namely alignment with efforts to improve Indonesia's EGDI. The researcher also actively participated in FGDs with five assessors in a forum for harmonizing perceptions and understanding of SPBE monitoring and evaluation data over the years. Data was also derived from the verification process through interviews between the researcher and the IPPDs under their responsibility. Over three years, interviews and verifications were conducted with 12 central institutions and 20 regional governments at the provincial, district, and city government

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levels. Each interview and verification lasted 100-120 minutes for each IPPD. Every year, the researcher was involved at least twice in presenting the progress and results of SPBE monitoring and evaluation among university assessors. Presentation notes at least provided data from ten assessors, with each presenting between 4 to 8 IPPDs. The analytical lens used in this research is institutional theory. It comprises three theories: institutional isomorphism, institutional logic, and institutional entrepreneurship.

The results of the analysis show that the initiatives carried out by the Indonesian government through the implementation of SPBE have a major influence on the achievement of EGDI in each measurement period. The indicators used to measure the SPBE index are in line with the three EGDI measurements. The SPBE measurement domain includes the policy domain, governance domain, management domain and service domain. Meanwhile, EGDI measurements include OSI, TII, and HCI. The institutional theory analysis lens on institutional isomorphism shows that changes are greatly influenced by coercive variables, namely the application of regulations and rules above. Institutional logic is more influenced by the image of digital progress and prosperity. Meanwhile, institutional entrepreneurship shows that leadership initiative and courage to make changes are strong factors that encourage digitalization changes in their institutions.

JEL Classification: O33, H83, I38

Keywords: e-Government, EGDI, SPBE, digital transformation, Indonesia, Institutional Theory.

Acknowledgment: This outcome was prepared in the framework of the project Overcoming Digital Divide in Europe and Southeast Asia “ODDEA” Project No. 101086381 Call: HORIZON-MSCA-2021-SE-01-1

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Intersectional Digital Divide in Indonesia

Agnieszka Choczyńska
AGH University of Krakow
Faculty of Management
Antoniego Gramatyka 10, 30-067
Kraków, 30-059
Poland
e-mail: agachocz@agh.edu.pl

Abstract

This paper analyses the digital gap in Indonesia in the intersectional framework. I consider several metrics, such as the ratio of the population accessing the internet, villages receiving mobile internet signal, and telecommunication expenditures. There is a substantial gap in internet usage and mobile internet availability in Indonesia, mostly related to Urban vs Rural division and disparities between provinces. On the contrary, the gender gap is minimal. I also find no inequality in telecommunication expenditures. The gaps in internet usage were converging in recent years, but this was not true for the gaps in internet availability. People in intersectional groups face the combination of one-dimensional inequalities, but there are none or minimal surplus effects.

JEL Classification: O33, D12, D63

Keywords: digital gap, internet usage, intersectional Inequalities

Acknowledgment: This outcome was prepared in the framework of the project Overcoming Digital Divide in Europe and Southeast Asia “ODDEA” Project No. 101086381 Call: HORIZON-MSCA-2021-SE-01-1

**Co-funded by
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Fintech Industry Development and its Impact on the Transformation of the Banking Structure in Leading Southeast Countries

Jun Jiang

National Institute of Development Administration (Nida)
148 Seri Thai Rd
Khlung Chan
Bang Kapi District
Bangkok 10240
Thailand
e-mail: aaronjiangjs@gmail.com

Abstract

The fintech industry has emerged as a disruptive force in the global financial landscape, with profound implications for traditional banking structures. This research investigates the development of the fintech industry and its impact on the transformation of banking structures in leading Southeast Asian countries. By employing a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative analysis of industry data with qualitative insights from key stakeholders, the study aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the dynamics at play. Examining the evolution of the fintech sector in Southeast Asia, including regulatory frameworks, technological innovations, and market trends. Analyzing the extent to which fintech adoption has reshaped traditional banking structures, including changes in market share, customer preferences, and service offerings. Identifying the drivers and barriers influencing the integration of fintech solutions within the banking ecosystem, with a focus on regulatory challenges, consumer trust, and industry collaboration. Assessing the broader implications of fintech-driven banking transformation on financial inclusion, stability, and economic development in the region.

JEL Classification: G23, G21, G28

Keywords: digitalization, fintech industry, banking structures, financial inclusion

Acknowledgment: This outcome was prepared in the framework of the project Overcoming Digital Divide in Europe and Southeast Asia “ODDEA” Project No. 101086381 Call: HORIZON-MSCA-2021-SE-01-1

**Co-funded by
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Digitalization Development of Family Businesses in Thailand

Justyna Juchniewicz

Krakow University of Economics

Department of Economics and Enterprise Organization, Institute of Computer Science,
Accounting and Controlling

Rakowicka 27

Krakow, 31-510

Poland

e-mail: jjastka@wp.pl

Abstract

In Thailand, family-owned businesses has been growing strongly and rapidly, collectively contributed about 28 trillion baht or 72% of total business value and over 50% of listed company are family-owned businesses or run by families. They embrace technology to ensure they can continue to serve the evolving needs of their colleagues, customers and family members focusing on value-add activities. With today's business ecosystem of continuous change and innovation, business will need to be able to adjust to new ideas and the next generation will be key driver to this success. As businesses around the world are transforming their organizations to be more digital while using data to tailor a customer-centric experience, Thai family businesses are failing to prioritize the digital transformation of their operations. Only 27% of family-owned businesses view improving digital capabilities as a top priority, while 25% believe they have strong digital capabilities. But the development of digitalization of family businesses in Thailand is very important because it can determine the strength and success of these companies in the present world.

JEL classification: O 33

Keywords: family business in Thailand, digital transformation, development of digitalization.

Acknowledgment: This outcome was prepared in the framework of the project Overcoming Digital Divide in Europe and Southeast Asia "ODDEA" Project No. 101086381 Call: HORIZON-MSCA-2021-SE-01-1

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

News Media Transformation in Southeast Asia: Finding New Business Models in the Digital Media Landscape

Masduki

Universitas Islam Indonesia
Department of Communication
Address: Jl. Kaliurang Km 14,5 Ngemplak, Sleman
Yogyakarta
Indonesia 55581
E-mail: masduki@uii.ac.id

Abstract

The arrival of digital technology affected the news media industry through promising virtually networked production that is built on data-intense models. To address how news media outlets are adopting new approaches to sustain their business, this paper reviewed approximately 100 literatures across Southeast Asia, a leading region within the Global South with a complex media system. We employ a qualitative method to present drivers of digital media transformation, identifying innovative media business models and their management futures. We find that the drivers of media transformation are complex, with uncertain sustainability. News organizations in Southeast Asia do not rely on unique income sources, but rather combine different models of funding. By deploying various digital news platforms, these media outlets are trying to meet the needs of their audiences and better identifying their segments, both of which determine their corporate survival. This study advances knowledge about digital economies in the media sector and news media business models.

JEL Classification: L82, O33, G34

Keywords: Business Model; Digital Economies; Digital Media Transformation; News Media; Southeast Asia; Media Sustainability

Acknowledgment: This outcome was prepared in the framework of the project Overcoming Digital Divide in Europe and Southeast Asia “ODDEA” Project No. 101086381 Call: HORIZON-MSCA-2021-SE-01-1

**Co-funded by
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How CBDCs are Shaping Foreign Trust in the EU: Exploring Acceptance Trends

Hussein Mkiyes

University of Economics in Bratislava,
Slovakia

Faculty of Economics and Finance,
Department of Economics.

Dolnozemska cesta 1/b, Petržalka

Bratislava, 852 35

Slovak Republic

Hussein.mkiyes@euba.sk

Jewel Kumar Roy

Széchenyi István University, Hungary,

Faculty of Economics

Egyetem tér 1, 9026 Hungary

Győr, 9026

Hungary

roy.jewel.kumar@sze.hu

Abstract

This paper investigates the perspectives of foreigners residing in the European Union (EU) towards digital currencies, especially attention to those from Hungary, Poland, Czech Republic, and Slovakia. We conduct a comparison of attitudes and awareness abroad and at home countries via surveys conducted in EU member states, including Hungary, Poland, Czech Republic, and Slovakia. The paper tries to understand the trends of acceptance and use of digital currencies by foreign residents; in this regard, the potential role of CBDC is considered. Here, our findings would clearly illustrate the fact that the level of trust, security, and observance of regulation by CBDC is comparably better than any of the other cryptocurrencies. By researching the factors that would drive the adoption of CBDC, we are able to detail some key characteristics of CBDC that may serve to reconcile EU cultural and regulatory differences. The evidence gathered reveals that CBDC is viewed positively by foreign residents because the central bank is a more familiar and trustworthy alternative in comparison with decentralized cryptocurrencies. Additionally, the study delves into the demographic factors influencing the preference for digital currencies, such as age, education level, and professional background. It highlights that younger, more educated expatriates with a background in finance or technology are more inclined towards adopting CBDCs. Moreover, the paper explores how the integration of CBDCs within existing financial systems can enhance financial inclusion and cross-border transactions, providing a seamless experience for foreign residents. The research underscores the potential of CBDCs to not only facilitate economic activities but also to strengthen the financial integration of expatriates within the EU, thereby contributing to a more cohesive economic environment.

JEL classification: E42, E58, F15

Keywords: Central Bank Digital Currency (CBDC), digital currency adoption, foreign residents, European Union, regulatory compliance.

Acknowledgment: This outcome was prepared in the framework of the project Overcoming Digital Divide in Europe and Southeast Asia “ODDEA” Project No. 101086381 Call: HORIZON-MSCA-2021-SE-01-1

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English Language Education for Future Innovators and Global Economic Shifts: A Comparison of Montenegro and Poland

Igor Ognjanović

Institute of Modern Technologies of Montenegro
Cetinjski put 46A/2
Podgorica, 81000, Montenegro
e-mail: igor.ognjanovic@gmail.com

Sanja Radusinović

Secondary electrotechnical school „Vaso Aligrudić"
Vasa Raičkovića 26
Podgorica, 81000, Montenegro
e-mail: sanjaidado@gmail.com

Jerzy Duda

AGH University of Science and Technology
Gramatyka 10
30-067 Kraków, Poland
e-mail: jduda@agh.edu.pl

Joana Duda

AGH University of Science and Technology
Gramatyka 10
30-067 Kraków, Poland
e-mail: joduda@agh.edu.pl

Abstract

Informatization and digital innovations are the latest trends in the global economy, which inevitably have an impact on the English language education, with several key aspects. First, globalization and EU integration impose English as the main language for communication, business, and any activity, including international education. Consequently, the methodological approach in teaching and English language curricula reforms must be applied to the contexts of application. Second, the rapid development of technologies and the COVID-19 pandemic have also imposed new approaches in education, including distance learning, virtual reality, and many others, which cannot be uniformly applied to all subjects and levels of education. Finally, the opening of national economies to international companies, which usually open local representative offices, impose professional training of the future workforce for fluent communication and cooperation. To understand the aspects, the research includes a comparative analysis of practices in the English language education of future digital innovators and experts in Poland and Montenegro, as EU country and pre-accession country, respectively, from the aspects of national economies, educational systems, and teaching/learning approaches.

JEL classification: I2, Z1, I3

Keywords: digitization, English education, global economy, national economies, cross-matching

Acknowledgment: This outcome was prepared in the framework of the project Overcoming Digital Divide in Europe and Southeast Asia “ODDEA” Project No. 101086381 Call: HORIZON-MSCA-2021-SE-01-1

Co-funded by
the European Union

Unlocking Efficiency: Assessing the Impact of PromptPay on Government Operations and Financial Transactions in Thailand

Aweewan Panyagometh

International College

148 Seri Thai road, Klongkum, Bungkum,
Bangkok, 10240

Thailand

e-mail: aweewan.m@nida.ac.th

Marisa Laokulrach

International College

148 Seri Thai road, Klongkum, Bungkum,
Bangkok, 10240

Thailand

e-mail: marisa.laokulrach@gmail.com

Anetta Čaplánová

University of Economics in Bratislava

Department of Economics, Faculty of
Economics and Finance

Dolnozemska cesta 1

Bratislava, 852 35

Slovakia

anetta.caplanova@euba.sk

Abstract

Information and Communications Technologies (ICT) play a crucial role in enhancing the effectiveness, efficiency, transparency, and accountability of government operations. PromptPay, a key component of Thailand's national e-payment initiative, was introduced to facilitate faster, more convenient, and secure financial transactions. According to the data in 2021, there were 68,639,304 IDs of PromptPay registration. This study aims to understand how e-payment systems enhance government efficiency by reducing corruption and boosting economic performance. The costs and benefits (CBA) associated with Promptpay have been gathered from a variety of credible sources since its launch in 2016. CBA is a fundamental tool employed in various fields to evaluate the feasibility of projects, policies, and interventions. The study focuses on three main features of PromptPay: e-donation, tax refund, e-social welfare, and another feature. This research contributes to understanding the benefits of a national e-payment system to the society.

JEL classification: H76, O17, I38

Keywords: Government Efficiency, E-payment Systems, Economic Performance

Acknowledgment: This outcome was prepared in the framework of the project Overcoming Digital Divide in Europe and Southeast Asia "ODDEA" Project No. 101086381 Call: HORIZON-MSCA-2021-SE-01-1

Co-funded by
the European Union

Digital Divide Among ASEAN Countries: Evidence from Vietnam, Philippines, Laos and Cambodia

Arlinah Abd Rashid

Universiti Teknologi MARA
Arshad Ayub Graduate Business School
Level 3, Kompleks Al-Farabi
Shah Alam, 40450
Malaysia
e-mail: arlinah@uitm.edu.my

Abstract

Digital transformation has been seen as engines of economic growth for many developing nations including the ASEAN members. This paper examines the distribution of enhanced technology capabilities among the four ASEAN members: Vietnam, Philippines, Laos, and Cambodia. Specifically, it analyzes key technological advancement indicators which include mobile cellular subscriptions, households with internet access, households with a computer, and fixed broadband subscriptions. By analyzing these metrics, the study seeks to provide a comprehensive overview of the current state of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) and digitalization in these countries. The research further investigates the convergence and divergence trends in ICT development among these four ASEAN countries, identifying areas of common progress as well as disparities. This analysis is crucial for understanding the technological landscape of these emerging economies and for guiding policy initiatives aimed at fostering inclusive digital growth within the ASEAN region. The findings will offer valuable insights into the regional digital divide and help inform strategies to promote balanced technological development across ASEAN.

JEL classification: O47, O57

Keywords: Digital divide, Catch-up, Beta convergence

Acknowledgment: This outcome was prepared in the framework of the project Overcoming Digital Divide in Europe and Southeast Asia “ODDEA” Project No. 101086381 Call: HORIZON-MSCA-2021-SE-01-1

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

Assessing Digital Infrastructure in Internet Use: A Comparative Study of Malaysia and Balkan Region

Muhamad Hilman Roselan

Universiti Teknologi MARA

Arshad Ayub Graduate Business School.

Shah Alam, 40450

Malaysia

e-mail: hilmanroselan@yahoo.com.my

Nataša Kovač

University of Donja Gorica,

Faculty of Applied Sciences

Podgorica, 81000

Montenegro

e-mail: natasa.kovac@udg.edu.me

Abstract

This study assesses the role of the digital infrastructure and internet in economic growth, focusing on Malaysia and other countries in Balkan Region. The literature review explores factors like internet affordance, quality, and availability, showing their impact on socioeconomic development. Technological affordances such as coverage and affordability significantly impact internet adoption and application across. High-quality and reliable connectivity can be a significant drive for user's subscriptions. Additionally, internet availability improves education, healthcare, and reduces inequalities in the population. The COVID-19 pandemic accelerated online services and exposed the urban-rural digital divide. The comparative analysis of Malaysia and other countries in Balkan Region showcases the transformative power of technology in emerging markets. The article concludes with the importance of closing the digital divide to achieve equitable socioeconomic outcomes globally as it is essential for achieving global socioeconomic equality.

JEL classification: L 86, R 11

Keywords: Internet Use, Internet Affordance, Internet Quality, Internet Availability

Acknowledgment: This outcome was prepared in the framework of the project Overcoming Digital Divide in Europe and Southeast Asia "ODDEA" Project No. 101086381 Call: HORIZON-MSCA-2021-SE-01-1

Co-funded by
the European Union

Towards a Cashless Society: Examining the Impact of Digital Infrastructure on ePayment Transactions (A Cross-Country Analysis)

Nor Hazirah Mohamad Shukri
Universiti Teknologi MARA
Arshad Ayub Graduate Business School
Shah Alam, 40450
Malaysia
e-mail: nhazirahshukri@gmail.com

Nataša Kovač
University of Donja Gorica
Faculty of Applied Sciences
Podgorica, 81000
Montenegro
e-mail: natasa.kovac@udg.edu.me

Abstract

The emergence of financial technology (fintech) has revolutionized the global financial landscape, significantly boosting electronic payment (ePayment) transactions. This study investigates the relationship between digital infrastructure and ePayment transactions across countries through a quantitative analysis approach. Secondary data from central banks and relevant agencies are used to explore factors such as the Electronic Government Development Index (EGDI), mobile and broadband subscriptions, internet users, access to electricity, and the availability of point-of-sale (POS) platforms. Focusing on a diverse range of countries from the EU-27 and Malaysia, the research employs regression modelling and comparative analysis techniques to elucidate the influence of digital infrastructure on ePayment transactions. Anticipated outcomes include identifying a positive relationship between the digital infrastructure and ePayment transaction, offering insights to promote ePayment adoption and harness digitalization for socio-economic advancement towards a cashless society.

JEL classification: G 02, G 20

Keywords: electronic payment, digital infrastructure, e-readiness, cashless society

Acknowledgment: This outcome was prepared in the framework of the project Overcoming Digital Divide in Europe and Southeast Asia “ODDEA” Project No. 101086381 Call: HORIZON-MSCA-2021-SE-01-1

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

Innovating Inclusivity: How Digital Startups are Shaping Digital Equity in Southeast Asia

Beni Suranto

Universitas Islam Indonesia
Department of Informatics
Yogyakarta, Indonesia
e-mail: beni.suranto@uui.ac.id

Rafał Kusa

AGH University of Krakow
Faculty of Management
Gramatyka 10
30-067 Krakow
Poland
e-mail: rkusa@agh.edu.pl

Abstract

The digital divide in Southeast Asia presents significant hurdles in achieving digital equity. This study delves into the crucial role that digital startups play in bridging this gap. Digital equity is defined as the state in which all individuals and communities possess the necessary information technology capacity to fully engage in societal, democratic, and economic participation. Digital startups, known for their technology focus, early-stage development, high growth potential, and scalability, are especially poised to tackle digital inclusion challenges. Using various frameworks such as the Digital Opportunity Index, Global Framework for Digital Inclusion, Digital Inclusion Benchmark, Inclusive Internet Index, and Roland Berger's Digital Inclusion Index, this study employs a multidimensional approach. By examining data from key startup ecosystems in Singapore, Indonesia, Malaysia, Thailand, Vietnam, and the Philippines, this research highlights the contributions of digital startups in enhancing access, skills, usage, and supportive environments that are essential for digital inclusion. Initial findings indicate that digital startups are indispensable in creating innovative solutions that improve digital accessibility and affordability. These startups are utilizing advanced technologies to provide cost-effective, scalable solutions that cater to underserved and marginalized communities. The study emphasizes the significance of supportive policies and ecosystem development, which have been identified in the ASEAN framework for promoting the growth of digital startups. This research not only sheds light on the innovative approaches of digital startups in Southeast Asia but also provides actionable insights for policymakers, industry stakeholders, and academia to foster an inclusive digital economy. The ongoing study aims to further explore the impact of these startups on digital equity, offering a roadmap for leveraging technological innovation to achieve comprehensive digital inclusion across the region.

JEL classification: O33, L26, O53

Keywords: digital startups, innovation, digital equity, sustainability, Southeast Asia

Acknowledgment: This outcome was prepared in the framework of the project Overcoming Digital Divide in Europe and Southeast Asia “ODDEA” Project No. 101086381 Call: HORIZON-MSCA-2021-SE-01-1

Co-funded by
the European Union

Comparison of International Indicators to Identify Digital Divide

Roland Zsolt Szabó

Széchenyi István University

Kautz Gyula Faculty of Business and Economics, Department of Corporate Leadership and Marketing

Egyetem tér 1.

Győr, 9026

Hungary

e-mail: roland.szabo@sze.hu

Abstract

There is a broad consensus among researchers and economic decision-makers that digitalization is important, but that the tools for measuring it are not uniform across regions of the world. As a result, the perception of the digital development of different regions or even companies may differ, and identifying the phenomenon of digital divide itself is not a simple task. Accordingly, the aim of this research is to compare and evaluate international indicators that can be used to identify digital divide and to make recommendations for the development of indicator systems. The research compares and draws conclusions from key indicators in Europe and Southeast Asia. The Digital Economy and Society Index, the Digital Index, the Digital Intelligence Index and the Digital Integration Index show that digital development can be assessed along a number of dimensions and indicators. Although the intent of each index is similar, the methodologies differ on how to measure digital divide, and the conclusions on which benchmark is the best are partly contradictory. However, they all have in common that a conscious effort must be made to overcome the digital divide.

JEL classification: O11, O33, O38

Keywords: DESI, industry 4.0, digital transformation, inequality, global development

Acknowledgment: This outcome was prepared in the framework of the project Overcoming Digital Divide in Europe and Southeast Asia “ODDEA” Project No. 101086381 Call: HORIZON-MSCA-2021-SE-01-1 and funded by the New National Excellence Program of the Ministry of Culture and Innovation, funded by the National Research, Development and Innovation Fund under the code number ÚNKP-23-5-SZE-111.

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

Digital transformation of small and medium-sized enterprises in V4 countries. Research results from data analysis and evaluation process on the use of websites and social media

Barbara Siuta-Tokarska

Department of Economics and Organization of Enterprises

Cracow University of Economics

Rakowicka 27

Cracow

Poland

e-mail: siutab@uek.krakow.pl

Katarzyna Żmija

Department of Economics and Organization of Enterprises

Cracow University of Economics

Rakowicka 27

Cracow

Poland

e-mail: zmijak@uek.krakow.pl

Abstract

Digitalization processes have a significant impact on almost every aspect of the functioning of modern societies and economies, including the development prospects of the business sector and their financial performance. The digital transformation of business, especially of small and medium-sized enterprises, is of particular concern to policy-makers and is also of interest to researchers. Progress in the digitalization of EU economies and societies depends on the effectiveness of the implementation of the European Digital Decade, which sets specific goals and targets to be achieved by 2030 in various areas. Among these, one of the key ones is the digitization of businesses, especially SMEs, which is crucial for the success and growth of the European economy. A special need to catch up on the implementation of digital technologies concerns small and medium-sized enterprises from the Visegrad Group countries, i.e. countries with similar civilisation, cultural, historical and socio-economic conditions - which already at the beginning of their path of integration with the EU were characterised by specific characteristics and differences in the structures of their economies in relation to the countries of the so-called 'old Union'. It is therefore reasonable to ask whether, in recent years, small and medium-sized enterprises in these countries have been able to meet the challenges and participate effectively in the digital transformation taking place globally. Taking into account the above premises, the research presented by the authors fits into the identified research gap concerning the lack of an in-depth comparative analysis of the level of digitisation of small and medium-sized enterprises from the V4 countries in 2017-2022 and the resulting conclusions for determining the types of these changes and their directions in the context of the so-called digital transformation of the above-mentioned entities. The research covered one aspect of the digitisation of enterprises concerning the use of websites and social media in small and medium enterprises. The research aimed to answer the following research questions: - What was the performance of small and medium-sized enterprises in the Visegrad countries in the years 2017-

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2022 with regard to digitisation in terms of the use of websites and social media? - How did these results compare with the average performance of small and medium-sized enterprises in the EU27? - What differences existed in this respect between the group of small and medium-sized and large enterprises and the analysed countries? - What are the challenges for small and medium-sized enterprises in the V4 countries in this respect? The research covered small and medium-sized enterprises from the Visegrad Group countries (Czech Republic, Slovakia, Poland and Hungary), i.e. entities employing from 10 to 49 employees and from 50 to 249 employees respectively. The analysis was based on data from the Eurostat database and covered the years 2017-2022.

JEL Classification: O33, L25, O52

Keywords: digitalization, Small and medium-sized enterprises, European Digital Decade, Visegrad Group countries

Acknowledgment: This outcome was prepared in the framework of the project Overcoming Digital Divide in Europe and Southeast Asia “ODDEA” Project No. 101086381 Call: HORIZON-MSCA-2021-SE-01-1

Co-funded by
the European Union

Global digitalization: analysis of selected indices with a focus on Poland and Thailand

Justyna Tora

AGH University

Faculty of Management, Department of Applications of Mathematics in Economics

ul. Gramatyka 10

Kraków, 30-067

Poland

e-mail: jtora@agh.edu.pl

Abstract

The level of digitalization varies greatly from country to country and is influenced by many different factors. To enable further development, it is crucial to analyze existing differences. In my work, I examine differences in the level of digitalization based on the Digitalization Index (DIGIX) for 98 countries worldwide, with a special focus on Thailand and Poland. In addition, the analysis examines the relationships between the DIGIX and other factors derived from the E-Government Development Index and the Global Talent Competitiveness Index. The work focuses on comparing the development of digitalization in Thailand and Poland with the development of digitalization in leading countries. In addition, quantitative analysis is used to examine the significance of differences between selected indicators in Europe and Asia, taking into account the regional breakdown.

Based on the results, there are some differences in the level of digitalization development between European and Asian countries. Particularly significant differences in index scores emerge when countries are divided into Asian and European regions. In Europe, digitalization is most advanced in the northern countries, while in Asia, it is the eastern and southeastern countries that are leading the way.

JEL classification: O33, O57

Keywords: digitalization, Poland, Thailand, DIGIX

Acknowledgment: This outcome was prepared in the framework of the project Overcoming Digital Divide in Europe and Southeast Asia “ODDEA” Project No. 101086381 Call: HORIZON-MSCA-2021-SE-01-1

Co-funded by
the European Union

The Impact of Online Coaching on Sport Performance – A Comparison Review Between Hungary and Thailand

Adrienn Veisz

Széchenyi István University of Győr
Egyetem Square 1
Győr, 9026
Hungary
e-mail: adri.veisz@gmail.com

Marisa Laokulrach

International College
148 Seri Thai road, Klongkum, Bungkum,
Bangkok, 10240
Thailand
e-mail: marisa.laokulrach@gmail.com

Aweewan Panyagometh

International College
148 Seri Thai road, Klongkum, Bungkum,
Bangkok, 10240
Thailand
e-mail: aweewan.m@nida.ac.th

Abstract

The integration of online coaching into sports is becoming increasingly popular nowadays, it effects athletic performance and coach-athlete relationship. For this reason, this study is aiming to identify the effects of online coaching on sports performance, while also identifying the potential differences and similarities between Thailand and Hungary.

The study examines through questionnaires the current state of online coaching both in Thailand and Hungary, considering the cultural and the technological differences, highlighting the opportunities for online coaching. The research attempts to discover obstacles and successful paths of digital coaching in sports, in these two countries, by using quantitative data, focusing on the experiences of athletes, coaches and sport managers, regarding the integration of digital coaching and its perceived effects on athletes' performance.

We expect that the research will gives us an important insight into the international conversation of how online coaching affects athletes' performance in various sports contexts.

JEL Classification: L83, O33, Z21

Keywords: digitalization, athletic performance, sports, online coaching

Acknowledgment: This outcome was prepared in the framework of the project Overcoming Digital Divide in Europe and Southeast Asia “ODDEA” Project No. 101086381 Call: HORIZON-MSCA-2021-SE-01-1

Co-funded by
the European Union

Applying Multi-Attribute Decision Making to Assist Decision-making Groups in Selecting Digital Health Implementation Strategies

Setya Winarno

Universitas Islam Indonesia, Department of Civil Engineering
Jl. Kaliurang Km 14.5 Sleman
Yogyakarta, 55584
Indonesia
e-mail: winarno@uui.ac.id

Sri Kusumadewi

Universitas Islam Indonesia, Department of Informatics
Jl. Kaliurang Km 14.5 Sleman
Yogyakarta, 55584
Indonesia
e-mail: sri.kusumadewi@uui.ac.id

Abstract

The purpose of this research is to use Multi-Attribute Decision Making (MADM) to select an implementation plan for digital health. First, the research conducted a pilot study in Tirto Rahayu Village, Galur Subdistrict, Kulonprogo District, Yogyakarta Province, Indonesia. The proposed approach has made use of both human and organizational resources. Four criteria were established: teamwork, leadership, collaboration, and individual factors. Three to four sub-criteria make up each criterion. In this study, fifteen different implementation strategies were presented. To create the criterion weights, five decision makers took part. Opinions are given using a pairwise comparison matrix. Modified Digital Logic (MDL) was used to process each matrix in order to derive weights using a geometric mean method. A review of the literature and suggestions from the Tirto Rahayu participants were used to create the choice matrix. Three MADM techniques were used to handle the data: Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP), Simple Additive Weighting (SAW), and Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS). Sensitivity analyses are performed in order to determine the best approach. According to the test results, TOPSIS has shown to perform the best, meanwhile AHP and SAW provided the lower sensitivity.

JEL classification: I12, C44, O32

Keywords: MADM, AHP, SAW, TOPSIS

Acknowledgment: This outcome was prepared in the framework of the project Overcoming Digital Divide in Europe and Southeast Asia “ODDEA” Project No. 101086381 Call: HORIZON-MSCA-2021-SE-01-1

Co-funded by
the European Union

Technology Transfer Centers as Support Instruments for SMEs— Comparative Analysis of Poland and Malaysia

Maciej Woźniak

Department of Economics, Finance and Environmental Management
AGH University of Science and Technology in Kraków
al. Adama Mickiewicza 30
30-059 Cracow
Poland
e-mail: mawozniak@agh.edu.pl

Abstract

The goal of the paper is to compare technology transfer centers in Poland and Malaysia. Therefore, the authors decided to use the comparative analysis method. The findings show that technology transfer and commercialization efforts both in Poland and Malaysia are on the right track. This demonstrates the universities' persistent dedication to turning research and innovative ideas into concrete products, as seen by the university's sustained growth in total product commercialization. It emphasizes the critical role that they play in promoting technological transfers, particularly for SMEs. The paper contributes to the macroeconomics theory in the area of public policy. Furthermore, it also provides insights into the theory of incentives, particularly in the field of non-financial support. The findings could be of interest to policymakers on macro and micro levels.

JEL Classification: O32, O38, O57

Keywords: Technology transfer, Commercialization, Universities, Public policy

Acknowledgment: This outcome was prepared in the framework of the project Overcoming Digital Divide in Europe and Southeast Asia "ODDEA" Project No. 101086381 Call: HORIZON-MSCA-2021-SE-01-1

Co-funded by
the European Union

Influence of Hindi Cinema on Tourism: Mapping Intercultural Dialogue between India and Europe

Sachin Bharti

Guru Gobind Singh Indraprastha University
University School of Mass Communication
Guru Gobind Singh Indraprastha University, Sector-16 -C, Dwarka
New Delhi-110078
India
Email: drsachin@ipu.ac.in

Abstract:

The power of films in cultivating the desire to travel cannot be undermined. Picturesque landscapes in Hindi Cinema go back to the times of Yash Chopra films. Switzerland as a popular destination amongst Indians is just one example of tourism being influenced by films. This study explores the film as media texts through a semiological analysis. This semiotic approach to chosen films creates a ripple effect by promoting intercultural dialogues between India and Europe by influencing travel related behaviours of people. It reflects upon the multiple outcomes that are a consequence of the films selected for this study. Such outcomes have been identified as the personal journey of the film character etc. Film induced tourism, in hindsight, also exhibits the changes in popular public opinion around culture. Visual attractions in the Hindi Cinema have played a key role in putting a lot of places on the tourism map for cinema goers. Conversely, this has also invoked desire amongst Europeans to visit India and explore its culture. This was so far reflected in mere visuals of Indian Films and has played a key role in fostering relations between India and Europe by means of tourism.

JEL Classification: Z33, Z13, L82

Keywords: Tourism, India, Europe, Media Studies, Film Studies

Co-funded by
the European Union

Analysis of the digital divide in developing countries

Ani Galstyan

Economic Research Centre LTD, UK

London

United Kingdom

e-mail: anigalstyan1@gmail.com

Abstract

The importance of digital assets and the need for further development in the area of resilient digital transformation has been highlighted in recent years by the COVID-19 pandemic. The current study aims to explore the digital divide in developing countries. In particular, the study focuses on statistical and graphical analysis of Digitalisation Indicators as well as analysis of the previous studies to identify economic, social, political or technological factors that contribute to the digitization gap in the case of developing countries. On the other hand, an empirical analysis of the macroeconomic impact of the digital gap on economic performance and growth has been carried out. The results show that the reasons for the digital divide in developing countries are underdeveloped infrastructure, the cost of digital technologies, limited education and literacy levels and language barriers. However, the low level of digitization harms economic performance and growth in emerging market economies.

JEL classification: O33, O11, O57

Keywords: digitization indicators, economic growth, productivity

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